

Research Article

Titanium alloy thin films on stainless steel for biocompatible applications and surgical tools

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Abstract: In this research work the performance of the Titanium alloys thin films for the application in medical is assessed. The main purpose of this research work is to check consistency of the titanium alloys with the living organisms' tissues in term of their biocompatibility. Thin films of Titanium Alloys (TiN, TiAlN and TiCN) were deposited on stainless steel using cathodic arc method. Titanium and Titanium alloys were used as targets. Inside deposition chamber vacuum was created up to 10⁻⁶ mili bar range using turbo molecular pump. XRD, SEM and AFM images were obtained to study the structure, surface morphology and roughness of the deposited thin films, respectively. Using Vickers hardness test thin films hardness was determined. The consistency of the Thin Films with the tissues of the living organisms was tested by biocompatibility tests. It is found that thin films own excellent adhesion as well as they can be utilized for the medical and commercial purposes.

Keywords: Titanium alloy, cathodic arc method, biocompatibility tests, Vickers hardness test

1. Introduction of Thin films

Thin film is a superficial layer of material having thickness in the range of nanometers, on any substrate deposited to modify the interaction properties of the surface. Thin film technology is playing a very important role in many fields by modifying the physical and chemical properties of surface layer of the substrate. A well-known example of thin film is the common plane mirror having a thin metal coating on the one side of the sheet of glass to create reflection. The method

of silvering was commonly used to make mirrors [1]. Now more recently sputtering method is used for the deposition of metal onto the substrate. In the area of coating innovation, organic and polymer thin films played and received fundamental role. Thin film quality relies on deposition technique, surrounding gas, supplied energy, pressure and surface of the substrate [2].

The advancement in the thin film technology during the 20th century has brought a technological breakthrough in many areas. Thin film technology is used in different industries including magnetic recording media, electronics of semiconductors, light emitting diodes, optical coating, hard coating, for the energy production (for example thin films solar cells), for the storage of energy (thin films batteries) and especially in medical field i.e for the thin films drug delivery, artificial limb coatings etc by providing the passive solution to many problems in these areas which were difficult to handle and paved a way for the development of new materials [3]. Basically, thin film technology was utilized in Silicon integrated circuits. These circuits have extensive uses in various fields. A further main field of thin films with a thickness of several microns, is used in wear protection for example, heat barriers coating, enhanced performance of these items as well as shield products from barometrical and thermal impacts [4].

1.1 Biocompatible Materials

Generally biocompatible materials are the materials which are consistent with the human body. These materials are used to build the artificial parts, rehabilitation parts, or the implants to get the place of naturally build human body tissues. Biocompatible materials are used inside the human body in either direct contact or in indirect contact. Using these contact methods the material is utilized to repair or replace the effected part of the human body. Sometimes Inside the human body any part of it gets affected. It may be because of the age or accident. This effected part needed to be replaced or repaired by the artificial material.

Biocompatible materials are divided into two categories. One is the living or once living biocompatible materials. Such type of biocompatible materials is used in many areas for example the tissues Engineering [5]. Other category is the synthetic biocompatible materials. Synthetic biocompatible materials can be organic or inorganic materials. Synthetic Biocompatible materials are defined as the materials (organic or inorganic) inserted inside the human body to repair or to take place the faulty tissues. The idea of such materials is widely used in the drugs-delivery system; sensors or the instruments are functioning out of the human body tissues but are in close contact with them. Artificial heart system is one of the best examples [6]. Now the

development and research in many different fields has provided the path to create innovative biocompatible materials. In this way a vast improvement can be made to the already existing biocompatible materials. The quality of the materials will get better and the treatment process will improve.

“Definitions of Bio-compatible materials” were aggregated by European Society of Biomaterials in 1986. A few of explanations for biocompatible materials and most significant conditions in the arena are documented in previous studies [7, 8].

Special biocompatible materials, that are well renowned in the field of implants are those materials utilized for the fixation purposes. This category also includes the materials used to replace the deceased hard tissues. The process of development in these materials has gone through numerous innovations. Especially this type of biocompatible materials involves the particular biomaterial systems i.e. metals, ceramic materials as well as polymers. These materials are used for instance in the bones reconstruction and for joint or teeth replacement.

For effective use of implant inside the human body, a sufficient degree of tolerance of material is needed. In other words a substantial level of biocompatibility is required [9]. The ability of materials for biocompatibility has been characterized as “capacity of material to perform for an appropriate host in a particular application” [6, 10]. This implies that the material or any leechable item from it will not bring about cell death, irritation to the tissues, or other damage to the cell or tissue function. Implanted material not just should be biologically safe and stable in term of biocompatibility and degradation, but they also need to meet with the organic requirements of structural biocompatibility. More precisely shape, internal structure and design of the implanted material should be adjusted in accordance with the properties of the tissues being substituted. Apart from these requirements, biocompatibility of the surface of the material plays a vital role because the surface has direct contact with the human body tissues. Hence it is important to expose the surfaces in terms of their chemical, physical, organic and morphological properties [11]. High requirements in biomedical applications are yet to be met, equally in joint and bone substitution and the healing and renewal of bone weaknesses. The compatibility with the human body is the main precondition for the choice of biomaterials, which should thus have some significant properties that will be durable for use in the body without rejection. It can be confidently declared that biocompatible metals will continue to be used as biomaterials in the

future with further improvements and new revolutionary bio-functionalities in the use of metals. The basic definition of Biocompatible Materials is given in the Table 1.

Table 1 Definition of Biocompatible Materials [7,9].

Biocompatible material	Non-practical product utilized as medical gadget, expected to communicate with human body.
Implants	Medical devices produced using single or additional materials which is deliberately put inside human body, sometimes absolutely or moderately covered underneath epithelial surfaces.
Prosthetic Devices	Devices which replace a stem, part or tissues within human body.
Synthetic organs	Medical devices which replace, to some degree or entire, functionality of the organs inside body.

1.2 Ti and Ti- alloys

In the past, Titanium was regarded as an uncommon metal. Now-a-days it is supposed as very important metal. Commercially Titanium is considered as a highly valued metal. Titanium was first introduced by an English man Gregor in 1790. Later on it was named as Titan by Klaproth during 1795. Titanium belongs to IV group and 4th period inside the periodic table of the elements. Chemically it is a transitional element. Charge number of titanium is 22 and its atomic weight is 47.9. As it is a transitional element, titanium has an incomplete filled d-shell within its electronic configuration [12]. The incomplete d-shell makes Ti enables to make a solid solution with the mostly substitutional elements possessing a size factor in the range of 20%. In the elemental form titanium possesses a very high melting point (1668⁰C). It has a hexagonally close packed crystalline shape (hcp) α up to the temperature of 882.5⁰C. When the temperature is further increased from this temperature titanium changes to body centered cubical structure (bcc) [13].

1.1.1 Solid tissue Replacements

Solid tissues have been regularly harmed because of accidents, age, and other different reasons. So these solid tissues are needed to be repaired or replaced by the other Tissues naturally or artificially. The replacement of the damaged tissues with the artificial tissues is done by the

process of surgery. The requirements of the implanted material are different and they depend upon the area where the material is to be implanted [14].

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of hard tissues in human body [14]

Because of the previously stated attractive qualities, Ti and Ti-alloys are generally utilized for hard tissues substitutions as a part of artificial bones, joints, and dental implants. As a hard tissues substitution, lower elastic modulus of Ti as well as Ti-alloys is commonly analyzed for the biomechanical advantage. Among the widest applications of Ti and Ti-alloys are artificial hips joints which are consisted of articulating bearings (thigh scalps, cups) and stem. The material should be implanted and must be positioned in such a way that it can naturally move inside the hips joint. Hips stems are secured completely too intramedullary canals of femoral, cups, which are articulating part of femur head, are utilized for fixing by ream out common hip bone socket to suit the design. Titanium and Ti-alloys are being regularly utilized as a part of knees joints substitution that comprise of a femur segment, tibia segment, and patellae. The schematic diagram of hard tissues in human body is shown in Figure 1.

2. Experimental Setup

Surface coating is a strong method to enhance the lifetime of materials used in an aggressive environment. While choosing the proper coating method and material, we cannot only make sure the substrate material to increase its service life. Also another purpose is to build the market price of prepared items. The trial on an industrial setup "Cathodic arc deposition system" was done at an industrial set up of "Quench Age" Sialkot. Industrial usage of modern cathodic arc system initiated during Soviet Union about 1960-1970. Later on in 70's Soviet Union

administration released utilization of this deposition technique toward western world. It received remarkable appreciation for generating of hard metallic coating which are wear and corrosion resistance.

2.1 Deposition of Films

For the thin films deposition the substrate is clipped on a substrate holder in a vacuum chamber. For gas cleaning the standard pressure is reduced to 10^0 Pascal and flow of argon gas is switched on. The utilization of inert gas inside a chamber to clean the substrate is suitable because it remove all kind of contamination particles. As the gas flow is kept on argon gas molecules enter inside the chamber and collided the substrate surface to remove all sort of impurities. Now clutched the source materials (titanium alloys) into chamber and resettled the gas pressure of deposition chamber about 2.3×10^{-2} Pascal. Nitrogen gas was introduced inside the chamber. The flow rate of gases was 132 cm and pressure of gases was 2 pound/ square inch. Small voltage, higher Direct current energy source had been maintained so that arc voltages were 30 volts while arc current maintained at 60A. Arc is started at an instant when a moving shutter is kept on front side to cathodic material. The substrate is continuous moved to achieve uniform thickness of film which is deposited on substrate. The substrate was based such as the biasing voltage was 150 volts in order to induce proper ion bombardment on the surface of substrate material. The temperature during deposition of chamber was noted 101^0C . The films deposition time is 7.5 minutes. A summary of deposition parameters can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2 Summary of Deposition Parameter

Items	Measurements
Substrate Material	316 Stainless Steel
Cathode Materials	TiN, TiAlN and TiCN
Reactive Atmosphere	Nitrogen Gas
Base Pressure	2.3×10^{-2} pa
Substrate Biasing	150 Volts
Arc Current	60A
Arc Voltage	30 Volts
Chamber Temperature	101^0C
Nitrogen Flow Rate	132 Sccm
Nitrogen Pressure	2 pound/squ.inch
Coating Color	Multi-colored
Deposition Time	7.5 Minutes

As the 60A of arc current pass between the electrodes it vaporizes the target Materials from cathode and plasma is achieved. The plasma is directed toward the substrate surface in the presence of Nitrogen gas form TiN, TiAlN and TiCN deposited upon stainless steel SS316L surface. Colors of Thin films deposited on SS316L are multi-colors.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 X-Rays Diffraction (XRD)

X-RAYS Diffraction patterns showing crystal structure of TiN, TiAlN as well as TiCN are depicted in the Figure 2 (a) (b) (c). For a TiN thin film, TiN peak with strong (2 0 0) grain is observed in the XRD patterns. The indexed peaks (2 0 0), are the miller indices of TiN, TiAlN and TiCN at diffraction angle $2\theta = 44.4^\circ$ while the miller indices (1 1 1) at 37° are that of TiCN. A broad peak appears at lower angle around 12° belongs to the substrate material. By introducing Aluminum and carbon elements, TiAlN and TiCN maintain the same cubic structure as that of TiN thin films. The Aluminum and carbon atom replaces part of the nitrogen atoms by forming TiAlN and TiCN in the films. It has also been observed from the XRD scan that the prominent peak positioned at 44° shifts towards higher Braggs angle as the content of Al and C is added which indicate the contraction of lattice by the incorporation of Al and C. It may be attributed the fact that the Aluminum radii being small in size as compared to radii of Titanium.

Figure 2 From left to right (a): XRD TiN, (b): XRD pattern of TiCN thin film and (b): XRD TiAlN

The crystal size was calculated with the help of Debye Scherer's formula and was found to be 13.47nm, 11.97nm and 16.26nm for TiN, TiAlN and TiCN respectively.

3.2 Surface Morphology

For the surface morphology Scanning electron microscopy was used. Figures show the surface morphologies of the deposited materials for various ranges of shots. Scanning Electron Microscopy of the deposited samples exhibits extremely even surfaces devoid of any cracks. The films deposited exhibit plane surface and the grain size was found to be typically in microns. The pictures of without treatment samples were extremely abrasive, nonhomogeneous as well as possessed numerous cracks whereas after deposition of Titanium alloys coatings the prepared samples were really distinct, homogeneous and even possessed negligible cracks. These images show that the films are created from the excellent particles. Number of pores as well as voids can be observed to grow upon the surfaces, probably owing to the enhanced bombardment and scribing consequences of ions irradiation upon surfaces of the deposition thin films. Figure 3 (a) (b) (c). For a TiN thin film, TiN peak with strong (4 0 0) grain is observed in the XRD patterns.

Figure 3 From Left to right (a): SEM TiAlN (b): SEM TiC (c): SEM TiN

3.3 Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM)

The coating morphology was analyzed by using Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM). A VeecoTM DI CP-11 was utilized for the topographical characterization. Silicon Etching probes, with a radius of 10nm and nominal constant of 40 N/m was used. Following Figures 4 (a), (b) and (c) show the 2-D Surfaces topographies of Titanium alloys (TiN, TiAlN, TiCN) deposited on stainless steel substrate for various numbers of shots. All the AFM images were taken in

different scan areas. Root mean square (rms) roughness was calculated using the AFM images. Roughness first decreases for 25 numbers of shoots and then starts increasing for forty-five number of shots. Such non-linear roughness may be because of the difference of in-flux of high energetic N-ions approaching on various spots of the tested films for different numbers of shots anyhow this can be observed that the roughness has increased as the focus shots number is increased apart from the thin films samples and settled for twenty five numbers of focus shots. The ion ejected inside plasma focus possess a vast power ranges within a fountain-like symmetry in their angular distributions [15]. Most of the ions have been ejected inside a smaller solid angle with anodic axis and so their flux starts increasing with increase in angle. It also shows that roughness should be distinct at distinct spots of the tested products; this is compatible with our outcomes which are displayed in Figure 4 (d).

Figure 4 From left to right (a): AFM image for TiCN (b): AFM image for TiAlN (c): AFM image for TiN (d): Graph of Roughness versus samples

3.4 Cytotoxicity test for biocompatibility

Cytotoxicity test was done by examining the cellular reaction to L 929 fibroblast cell. Direct interaction process centered on ISO-10993- 5 was done upon the tested specimen. All the samples were sterilized by gamma-rays from ^{60}Co source [16]. Mice fibroblast cells (L929,

ATCC, USA) were grown inside culture flask along Dulbecco's minimal necessary medium formulated with 10% fetal bovines serum and placed inside incubator at 37⁰C under 5% CO₂ and low humidity for 2 days [17]. The liquid extracts were utilized to culture L929 mouse fibroblasts cells inside twenty four well plates utilizing Trypsin-EDTA solution for 2 days. In order to find out the impacts of direct contact between the test samples (thin films) and L929 cells, as soon as the cells achieved confluences, tested samples were placed on the confluent cells layer. At 3rd day of culture, cell morphology and cell death were observed using cytotoxicity test based on ISO-10993-5 standard [18]. The samples were critical point dried and viewed under the microscope.

No cytotoxic effect was seen for any of the material presented for the test, when it was compared to fresh culture medium (negative control). No change in the cell death or cell morphology was observed on direct interaction with coated films as depicted in the Figure 5 (a,b,c,d). So these results show the coated films are not cytotoxic and may be supposed for the biomedical uses.

Figure 5 From left to right (a): Microscopic image of CP-Ti (b): Microscopic image TiN (c): Microscopic image of TiCN (d): Microscopic image of TiAlN [19]

4. Conclusion

Thin films of Titanium alloys including TiN, TiAlN, TiCN were deposited on stainless steel substrate using cathodic arc method. The vacuum of the chamber was maintained at 6×10^{-6} mbar. Films were analyzed by using XRD, SEM, AFM and their Cytotoxicity tests (Biocompatibility tests) were also conducted. In this work the performance of the coatings was examined for biocompatible purposes in term of their surface qualities and Cytotoxicity. Because of high corrosion resistance of prepared samples coating, they can be implanted inside the human body to replace the effected part where high corrosion resistance is required. All these prepared thin films also possess very good hardness so they can be used for the preparation of surgical tools. All Three coatings presented for test gives the similar results. All the coatings have similar properties, topography and Possess good biocompatibility. All the thin films are not cytotoxic and can be used for the Medical applications.

References

- [1] Kiyotaka Wasa, Makoto kitabatake and Hideaki Adachi, Thin film materials technology Sputtering of Compound Materials, 1st edition, (springer ,2004).
- [2] K.S. Sree Harsha, Principal of physical vapor deposition of thin films, 1st edition, (Elsevier ,2006).
- [3] A.Kumar, Y.W Chung, J.J Moore and J.E. Smuleresky, Surface Engineering, Science and Technology , The Minerals, Metals and Materials Society , Warrendale , page 177 (1999).
- [4] A. Kumar, Y.W. Chung and R.W.J. Chia, Hard Coatings,The Minerals, Metals and Materials Society, 153-168 (1998).
- [5] BD. Ratner, AS.Hoffmann, FJ. Schoen, Lemons, Biomaterials science, An introduction to materials in medicine, 3rd edition, (Academic Press, 1996).
- [6] JS.Temenoff, G .Mikos Antonios, Biomaterials: The intersection of biology and materials science, 1st edition, (N.J.: Pearson/Prentice Hall. 2008).
- [7] DF. Williams, C .In: de Potter, K .de Lange, K.de Groot, AJC .Lee, Consensus and definitions in biomaterials, editors. Advances in biomaterials. Amsterdam, 6-11 (Elsevier ,1987).
- [8] BD. Ratner, DM. In: Brunette, P. Tengvall, M. Textor, P. Thomson , A perspective on titanium biocompatibility, editors ,Titanium in medicine and material science, surface science, engineering, biological responses and medical applications, 2–12 (Springer; 2001).

- [9] Wintermantel Erich, Ha suk-woo, biocompatible materials and procedures, 3rd edition, Berlin (Springer, 2002).
- [10] KHJ. Buschow, RW .Cahn, MC. Flemings, B. Ilschner, EJ. Kramer, S.Mahajan, Encyclopedia of materials, 1st edition (Elsevier, 2001).
- [11] RK .Schenk, OCC. In: Lin, CEY .hao, Bone response to grafts and implants. editors. Perspectives on biomaterials: proceedings of the 1985 international symposium on biomaterials, 121–136 (Elsevier, 1986).
- [12] DD. Tirrell, Hierarchical structures in biology as a guide for new materials technology, National research council (US) committee on synthetic hierarchical structures, vol. xii , 130 (Nlab, 1994).
- [13] NM. Hancox, Biology of bone, 1st edition (Cambridge Eng.: University Press, 1972).
- [14] D. Currey John, The mechanical adaptations of bones. Princeton, 1st edition (N.J.: Princeton University Press,1984).
- [15] R. Lakes ,Materials with structural hierarchy, A review article (Nature publishing group,1993).
- [16] P. Frasca, RA. Harper, JL. Katz, Isolation of single osteons and osteon lamellae, Acta Anat, 95-122 (1976).
- [17] D. Enderle John , D. Bronzino Joseph, M. Blanchard Susan., Introduction to biomedical engineering, 2nd edition, Amsterdam ;Boston, (Elsevier Academic Press; 2005).
- [18] H.R. Ogden, A.H. Clifford (Ed.), Rare Metals Handbook, Rinhdd Publishing Corporation, Chapman & Hall Ltd., London, 559–579,(1961).
- [19] E.W. Collings, The physical metallurgy of titanium alloys, in: H.L. Gegel (Ed.), ASM Series in Metal Processing, Edward Arnold Publications, Cleveland, Metals Park, 559-579 (1984).

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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